

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon-MSCA Staff Exchange 2022 program under the grant agreement 1011361612.

Project: 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys –HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
 Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D8.1

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN AND COMMUNICATION “TOOLKIT”

Due Date of Deliverable	M6	Completion Date of Deliverable	15/11/2024
Deliverable leading partner	UPM	Author	Blanca González
Signed off by		Person	Gustavo R. Plaza
WP no.	WP8	WP Title	Management
Dissemination level	Public		

Start date of the project	01/11/2024	Duration	48 months
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Version	V1.0	Status	Final Version
Version Log			
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Coordinator:

Participants (3):

Partners (4):

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1

Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the communication and dissemination plan and communication “toolkit”

The purpose of this report is to plan the dissemination of (non-confidential) results of the project by all partners and to communicate about the project to the public, with activities and measures targeting all project's stakeholders. This report presents the communication and dissemination (C&D) strategy visioned for the project 1011361612–SameMultiPhys–HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01, aiming to ensure targeted and well-thought outreach activities to boost the impact of the project, along with the implementation of the C&D activities efficient and measurable, carried out during the project, including but not limited to:

- The press release announcing the project.
- The launch of the SameMultiPhys website.
- The set-up of the social media channels.
- The preparation of the project visual identity (logo) and templates (Word and Power Point documents).

This document is composed of two main parts: the **C&D plan** and the **C&D activities**. This latter has been produced with the contribution from the partners reporting to UPM about their C&D actions during the first year of the project. Further reports about C&D and networking activities during the project lifetime will be prepared in a collective effort from the whole consortium coordinated by UPM.

1.2 Relation to other project documents (deliverables)

The project kicked off in November 2023 and will last until October 2027. This deliverable was made public 6 months after the due date, in October 2024, as there were administrative delays in the signature of the Consortium Agreement (CA), which took one year to be signed by all parties. In spite of this delay, as shown in this report, all planned C&D activities and measures have been planned for implementation during the project's duration.

The C&D plan has been conceived by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) as Coordinator and has received the final approval the other from the other beneficiaries of the project. In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Communication and Dissemination Plan and Communication “toolkit” is overruled by Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

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Communication and dissemination strategy

2.1 Communication and dissemination (C&D) workplan

The **C&D plan** of SameMultiPhys project has the general objective of disseminating and promoting the scientific and technological results, as well as the importance of the research and advances made in the project, to generate impact and engage the various audiences interested in it. Its **specific objectives** are the following:

- Increase the visibility and impact of the scientific and technological results of the project.
- Communicate the results to the scientific community and stakeholders.
- Establish new contacts and develop new collaborations with researchers, research groups, and other consortia/networks at the national, European, and international levels.
- Raise public awareness of the project's impact.

This C&D plan embraces the analysis of the **target audiences** and **stakeholders** to whom the SameMultiPhys project wishes to reach out, the **dissemination channels** through which the consortium will communicate with the outside world. The plan also includes a broad overview of the potential **events** where the project results can be disseminated, and it attempts to draw a map of **scientific journals** as well in order to assess the complementary outreach to specific target groups. An important corner stone of the networking activities will be the liaison with other **relevant projects and initiatives** to mutually support one another and increase the impact delivered by each of them. The **C&D plan** is sub-divided into several steps, which are presented in this chapter.

2.2 Target audience and project stakeholder groups

The target audiences for communication and dissemination activities include (a) **scientific and academic researchers and non-clinical researchers** (i.e. media and end-users), (b) **companies and investors** as well as (c) **general public**. Academic researchers, particularly in cellular biology, biophysics, mechanobiology and related fields, are a primary audience. They will benefit from the microfluidic tools developed through the project, which can enhance their research on cell mechanobiology. Industry professionals, including engineers and experts in microfluidics, are also targeted, as they are likely to seek innovative tools to improve their work in cellular research and diagnostics. Furthermore, healthcare and clinical researchers focusing on applications in immunology, cancer research, and tissue engineering can leverage the findings from the SameMultiPhys project to advance their work

In terms of stakeholders, the project involves (i) research institutions participating in the project, which contribute their expertise and resources to the initiative; (ii) the European funding agency, which provides the financial support necessary for research, development, and dissemination activities; (iii) industrial partners, including companies specializing in microfluidic technologies and related products, who may collaborate with the project or benefit from its findings; (iv) the broader scientific community is another significant stakeholder; finally, (v) the general public stand to benefit from the advancements in healthcare and diagnostics that arise from the project's research.

2.3 Communication channels

The communication channels of the project, classified into internal and external channels, are listed below. Internal dissemination channels refer to those directed at internal stakeholders, such as consortium members or partner organizations. External dissemination channels are aimed at the broader public, potential collaborators from academia or industry, or the scientific community.

2.3.1 Internal dissemination channels

→ (a) *Visual identity: specific logo, branding and communication templates*

The design of the project visual identity started from the conception of the project logo (Figure 1), along with relevant graphic aspects (e.g., fonts, colours), which constituted the reference for the subsequent design of all other graphic elements: headers and backgrounds for website and social media, templates (Figure 2 and 3). The branding was defined between M1 and the beginning of M3 (November 2023 – January 2024) and relevant materials are all available for Consortium consultation on the shared online repository, in both vectorial and rendered formats (Figure 4 and 5).

Figure 1: SameMultiPhys logo

SameMultiPhys

Figure 2: SameMultiPhys logo acronym symbol

Figure 3: SameMultiPhys logo acronym + full title

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Project: 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys –HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D1.1 HANDBOOK OF MANAGEMENT

Due Date of Deliverable	M3	Completion Date of Deliverable	21/03/2024
Deliverable leading partner	UPM	Author	Bianca González
Signed off by		Person	Gustavo R. Plaza
WP no.	WP1	WP Title	Management
Dissemination level	Public		

Start date of the project	01/11/2024	Duration	48 months
Version	V1.0	Status	Final Version
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Figure 4: Word template of the project's deliverables

HORIZON-MSCA STAFF EXCHANGE 2022
NOVEL BIOPHYSICAL TOOLS TO MEASURE MULTIPLE PARAMETERS IN THE SAME CELL
Action 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys

Coordination Team
Kick-off Meeting
Online meeting, November 29th 2023

1. Welcome and meeting overview

Gustavo Plaza (UPM), Coordinator

AGENDA

Time (CEST)	Session	Speaker
14:00-14:15	Welcome and meeting overview	Gustavo Plaza, Coordinator (UPM)
14:10-14:15	Preliminary ideas for the proposed project	Gustavo Plaza (UPM)
14:15-14:45	EC Welcome: Characteristics of MSCA SE projects	Project Officer (CE)
14:45-15:00	WP1 Project Management	Bianca González (UPM)
15:00-15:15	WP2 Design and fabrication of prototypes	Pierre Joseph (CNRS)
15:15-15:30	WP3 Standardizing measurements with calibration samples	Cristina Morillo (INMFI)
15:30-15:45	WP4 Testing and validating prototypes	Pierre Joseph (CNRS)
15:45-16:00	Coffee Break	
16:00-16:15	WP5 Quantifying images and performing statistical analysis	Yael Roichman (TAU)
16:15-16:30	WP6 Refine: Evaluation of the prototypes for improvements	Gustavo Plaza (UPM)
16:30-16:45	WP7 Development of biophysical models of cell response	Gustavo Plaza (UPM)
16:45-17:00	WP8 Dissemination and communication	Bianca González (UPM)
17:00-18:00	Presentation of associated partners	Claudia Garcia (SACCH), Juan C. Del Alamo (UV), Liam J. Holt (NYU) and Crisp Simmons (UTL)
18:00-18:15	Transfer of knowledge during the project	Bianca González (UPM)
18:15-18:30	Conclusions and questions	

PROJECT SUMMARY

Project number: 1011361612
Project name: Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell
Project acronym: SameMultiPhys
Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Topic: HORIZON-TMA MSCA Staff Exchanges
Type of action: HORIZON-TMA MSCA Staff Exchanges
Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency
Grant managed through EU Funding & Tenders Portal: Yes (eGrants)
Project starting date: fiscal date: 1 November 2023
Project end date: 31 October 2027
Project duration: 48 months
Consortium agreement: Yes

Figure 5: PowerPoint template of the project's presentations

→ (b) Project's website

URL: <https://blogs.upm.es/mechanobiology/samemultiphys/>

Hosting the SameMultiPhys project website on the UPM de server for researchers' blogs provides numerous benefits that enhance its credibility and accessibility within the academic community. The UPM platform, optimized for academic content, ensures ease of navigation and accessibility, while facilitating integration with other related research initiatives, promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing. Additionally, UPM offers technical support, maintenance, tracking of statistics and security, allowing the SameMultiPhys team to focus on their research without the burden of website management. The blog format encourages user engagement through comments and discussions, fostering a vibrant community around the project. Furthermore, the university's strong domain authority enhances the site's search engine optimization, making it more discoverable to those seeking related information. Utilizing existing university resources can also be cost-effective, avoiding the need for external hosting services. Lastly, the long-term sustainability of a university-hosted website ensures that valuable research resources remain accessible even after funding ends, further solidifying the impact and reach of the SameMultiPhys project within the scientific community.

The website of the project will serve as an 'online presence' and repository where all relevant information, results, and news related to the program are published in an organized and accessible manner. The SameMultiPhys website was launched immediately after the consortium agreement was signed. The website, as shown in Figure 4, includes the minimum content required by the grant agreement, such as title, description, reference in CORDIS, social media channels and contact us form. It details the research groups participating in the project, in addition to the interdisciplinary dimensions of the project. It also promotes the program's seminars, publications, and featured news. Website statics will be tracked using the plugin Google Analytics GA4.

SameMultiPhys

**Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters In The Same Cell
(HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01-01. Grant agreement ID: 1011361612)**

The Group of Mechanobiology of the Center for Biomedical Technology coordinates the project *SameMultiPhys*, founded under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) of the European Commission (*Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters In The Same Cell*, Topic: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01-01. Grant agreement ID: 1011361612, duration: 2023-2027. DOI: 10.3030/1011361612).

You can find more details about the project on [the CORDIS web](#) and follow the project's [LinkedIn](#) and [X](#) profiles for updates.

Figure 6: SameMultiPhys website: <https://blogs.upm.es/mechanobiology/samemultiphys/>

→ (c) Social media channels

Social networks will be used during the project as communication channels for dissemination and news. Each post is carefully targeted toward its intended audience (considering characteristics, comprehension levels, and interests).

A LinkedIn profile <https://www.linkedin.com/company/samemultiphys/> and a X profile <https://x.com/SameMultiPhys> were created for SameMultiPhys (Figures 5 and 6) after the consortium agreement was signed by all parties.

Figure 7: SameMultiPhys's LinkedIn Profile. URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/samemultiphys/>

Figure 8: SameMultiPhys's X Profile. URL: <https://x.com/SameMultiPhys>

→ (d) *Audiovisual material for publications*

Short informational publications, with 2 photos or a video about the project (around 1-minute videos) will be produced. The audiovisual material for the publications will feature:

- Principal investigators from each group explaining their role and objectives within SameMultiPhys.
- Short interviews with SameMultiPhys seconded researchers, summarizing key aspects of the secondments, aimed at making the project accessible to a general audience (using simple, non-technical language).
- How to use the tools developed by the project.
- For what purpose you use the tools developed by the project and what results one can obtain.
- What benefits society gains in SameMultiPhys research.

These materials will be published on the SameMultiPhys website and the YouTube channel of the Center for Biomedical Technology (www.youtube.com/@ctbuniversidadpolitecnica4976) at UPM. They aim to increase traffic to the project's website and social media channels, raise awareness among colleagues and friends about everything SameMultiPhys has to offer, and enhance the positioning of the tools developed in the project by highlighting why they are the ideal choice for advanced research in cellular mechanobiology.

2.3.2 External Dissemination Channels

→ (e) *Websites of project's beneficiaries*

Beneficiaries' websites: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (<https://www.upm.es/>); Center for Biomedical Technology (<http://www.ctb.upm.es/>), LAAS-CNRS (<https://www.laas.fr/en/>), Università degli studi di Firenze (<http://www.unifi.it/it>), Tel Aviv University (<https://english.tau.ac.il/>)

→ (f) *Social media of project's beneficiaries*

Beneficiaries' social media: LinkedIn of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and X of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (@La_UPM), X of LAAS-CNRS (@LaasCNRS), X of Università degli studi di Firenze (@UNI_FIRENZE) and X of Tel Aviv University (@TelAvivUni).

→ (g) *Social media of the CTB (X, LinkedIn) and YouTube platform*

The social media channels of the Center for Biomedical Technology will be used, where the research laboratory of the coordinator of the program is located, both on LinkedIn and X (@CTBUPM), given that the number of followers and contacts is larger and more consistent over time than the profile created for the program. This will help with the dissemination of events, results, and news related to SameMultiPhys. The developed audiovisual material will also be published on the CTB's YouTube channel, given their broader reach.

→ (h) *Press releases*

A press release has been submitted to the UPM press office after the start of the project, once that the consortium agreement was signed, and at the end of the project at the website of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. There will be interim releases for significant development.

2.4 Dissemination Events

Partners will be encouraged to participate in conferences related to the project's topics, to disseminate project activities. The dissemination events for the project will include:

- Contributions at scientific and technological conferences and congresses.
- Organization of seminars and workshops.
 - Seminars about project updates and progress. These seminars will facilitate discussions and feedback sessions where researchers of the project can engage in constructive conversation about the findings and outcomes of their work.
 - Workshops will include training sessions or workshops on specific techniques, software tools or methodologies relevant to the project. These workshops will help researchers enhance their skills and expand their expertise, contributing to the overall progress of the project.
- Participation in science outreach events: Participation in Science Week, International Day of Women and Girls in Science, and workshops targeted at young people and children, among others.

These events will be announced on the SameMultiPhys website to showcase the project results to stakeholders.

2.5 Scientific publications

The findings of SameMultiPhys to the scientific community will be disseminated in open access, peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals indexed in the Journal Citations Reports database (JCR). To maintain transparency and reproducibility, the underlying data, protocols, and methods will also be shared, where possible, in alignment with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. Special emphasis will be placed on publishing in high-impact and interdisciplinary journals to reach a broader readership.

2.6 Final overview of the C&D plan

Taking into account our target audience, we will focus our dissemination and outreach actions as follows:

1. **Scientific and academic researchers and non-clinical researchers in the sector:**
 - Contributions at scientific and technological conferences and congresses.
 - Scientific publications.
 - Organization of seminars and workshops.
 - Training activities: specialized seminars by PIs of the project to train (post)-graduate students.
 - Development and dissemination of scientific-technological services offered by the consortium.
2. **Companies and investors in the sector:**
 - Digital media: website and social media.
 - Outreach materials: videos, news.
 - Dissemination in the media.
3. **General public:**
 - Digital media: website and social media.
 - Outreach materials: videos, news.
 - Science outreach activities: Science Week, International Day of Women and Girls in Science, workshops aimed at youth and children, etc.

2.7 Indicators

For the successful implementation of the Communications & Dissemination Plan, the following indicators will be measured during the project:

Table 1 – Evaluation: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Dissemination success indicator	Indication	Phase I (General promotion and strategy planning) M1-M12 OBJECTIVE 1. Create expectation and general promotion	Phase II (Dissemination and communication activities) M13-M42 OBJECTIVE: Building a value-based stakeholder network	Phase III (Finalisation) M43-M48 OBJECTIVE. Capitalise on results and leave a mark
Communication web impact	Quantitative: Accesses report/number	500	1000	2000
Impact on social media	Quantitative: Accesses report/number	500	1000	2000
Dissemination: audiovisual materials	Quantitative		2	4
Publications	Quantitative	1	2	4
Relevant events, workshops, seminars organized by SameMultiPhys	Quantitative	1	2	4
Relevant events, conferences, workshops, seminars organized by others in which SameMultiPhys participates at international level	Quantitative	1	2	4
Relevant events, conferences, workshops, seminars and outreach activities organized by others in which SameMultiPhys participates at national, regional, local level	Quantitative	1	2	4
Press releases	Quantitative	1	2	2
Annual virtual meetings	Quantitative	1	3	4

3

Implementation: communication and dissemination activities

3.1 Dissemination, outreach and exploitation: M1-M12 activities

The following activities related to dissemination, outreach and exploitation have been completed during the first year of the project:

1. Creation of the logo of the project (see Figures 1-3).
2. Presentation templates. Word and Power Point templated have been shared with all Consortium Members via email and have been upload on the online communication and repository tool.
3. Website of the project, under URL: <https://blogs.upm.es/mechanobiology/samemultiphys/>
4. Social media of the project: A LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/samemultiphys/> and a X profile <https://x.com/SameMultiPhys> were launched. (Figures 5-6)
5. Seminar about project updates and progress's updates to the MILE team, directed by Pierre Joseph, during the first secondment of the project at LAAS-CNRS of Toulouse on 02/09/2024 at 10:00 (ECT), by Blanca González Bermúdez (UPM) and Pierre Joseph. Title of the seminar: "SameMultiPhys Project: Multiple Biophysical Measurement on Single Cells". Location: [LAAS](#) (CNRS, Toulouse).
6. A press release has been submitted to the UPM press office (full draft completed and pending for online publication of the website on November 25, 2024)

3.2 Indicators and Impact Evaluation of C&D Activities (M1-M12 activities)

Table 2 – Indicators and impact evaluation of SameMultiPhys Communication and Dissemination Plan during the first year of the project (November 2023, October 2024).

Communication channel	Impact Indicators
Websites	
https://blogs.upm.es/mechanobiology/samemultiphys/	Nº of visits: 4 (Google Analytics 17/10/2024-13/11/2024) Nº of visitors: 4 Nº of events published: 2
http://www.ctb.upm.es/dissemination/	Visits from the SameMultiPhys website from this web (banner of the project): 2
https://www.upm.es/	Nº of published press releases: 1
Social media channels	
LinkedIn SameMultiPhys	Followers: 21 Page views: 64 Unique visitors: 24 Nº posts: 1 Nº total impressions: 137/post Nº of reposts: 1 Nº of total impressions of repost: 385/repost
X SameMultiPhys (@SameMultiPhys)	Followers: 43 Nº posts related to SameMultiPhys: 1 (12 impressions) Nº of likes in posts related to SameMultiPhys: 1 Nº reposts related to SameMultiPhys: 1

LinkedIn CTB	Followers: 2218 Contacts: more than 500 N° posts related to SameMultiPhys: 0
X CTB (@CTBUPM)	Followers: 1029 N° posts related to SameMultiPhys: 0 (0 impressions) N° of likes in posts related to SameMultiPhys: 0 N° reposts related to SameMultiPhys: 0
Audiovisual material for publications	
Short videos of SameMultiPhys	N° of videos: 1 published video in CTB's Youtube channel (0 views)
Dissemination events	
Events organized from SameMultiPhys. Tota: 2	N° Seminars/Workshops about progress of SameMultiPhys: 1 N° Seminars in the "CTB-MINA Biomaterials and Neurotechnology" series: 1
Conferences	0 communications in conferences and congresses
Publications	0 articles (0 Open Access; 0 published in Q1)
Press releases	1 press released pre-approved by Communication UPM

4

Conclusions and Next Steps

This report includes all essential elements required in a comprehensive dissemination plan: objectives, target audiences, key messages, project visual identity, and communication toolkit, as well as dissemination materials, methods, activity planning, and evaluation plans for all dissemination activities.

The dissemination plan provides the SameMultiPhys project with a robust framework for effectively sharing project results and activities. This will serve as an initial strategy for the consortium, which will be reviewed, refined, and updated as the project progresses. Dissemination materials and activities will be assessed for their outreach, effectiveness in engaging stakeholders, and alignment with stakeholder interests and potential barriers.

The branding for the SameMultiPhys project has been detailed. Additionally, this report outlines SameMultiPhys Dissemination Key Performance Indicators, which will be monitored throughout the project's duration. All SameMultiPhys partners are involved in dissemination activities, with scheduling included in this report.

The main goal of Phase I was to establish the foundations of the project C&D activities, develop the tools, the visual identity and the templates and launch the first promotional activities, let the external world know about the start of the project at events and on social media. The first C&D activities/actions during were successfully planned but also implemented with some delay due to the signature process of the consortium agreement. The objective for the upcoming period is to implement the C&D plan during Phase II and III.